

1 **Casz1 mobilization during TE lineage specification from the pluripotent state in embryonic stem**
2 **cells.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Casz1
9 as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

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